

The Influence of Service Quality and Cost Perceptions on Trust and Its Implications for Patient Satisfaction at RSU AMIRA Purwakarta

Purna Irawan¹; Yuli Harwani²

Master of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business
Mercu Buana University Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- The primary objective of this research is to investigate and assess the direct and indirect impacts of patient trust as a mediator between patient satisfaction and perceptions of service quality and cost. This is a quantitative descriptive research design. Two hundred outpatients from AMIRA Regional Hospital were selected using a non-probability purposive selection method. Version 3.0 of the smartPLS SEM (Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling) program was used to analyze the data for this study. The findings of this study indicate that price perception on trust has a significant positive effect on trust (T-statistic value of 2.133 and T-table value of 1.972), The impact of service quality on satisfaction is positively and significantly related to trust (T-statistic value of 11.96 and T-table value of 1.972), as is the impact of pricing perception on trust (T-statistic value of 2.133 and T-table value of 1.972). In addition, it may be inferred that each variable has a statistically significant and positive indirect influence if the T-Statistics value is more than the crucial value from the T-Table and the P-Value is less than 0.05.

Keywords:- Service Quality, Cost, Trust, Patient Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hospitals are centers for many types of medical professionals, medicines, and patients. In the beginning, hospitals functioned as social institutions; Nevertheless, the emergence of private hospitals has transformed the healthcare sector into a commercial entity in its own right, with management practices rooted in business entity theory, leading to increasingly intense competition. Likewise, the public or patients who wish to undergo treatment at a hospital can first seek information about the hospital they are going to. This information can include how services are provided, facilities available, doctors who treat patients, prices offered and so on as a reference for treatment trust. Searching for the information obtained will be the decision to choose a hospital to treat the disease. Apart from that, the performance of hospitals that have spread among the community is also one of the considerations when choosing a hospital. Hospitals, both publicly and privately managed, face increasing levels of competition as a result of increasing patient loads and other factors. To stay ahead of the competition, hospital

administration must effectively implement its vision and goals for the benefit of all stakeholders by developing strategies that focus on patient needs. The capacity to survive, overcome limited resources, and face competition are all facilitated by these advantages, which in turn enable hospitals to achieve their goals with demonstrable results. There is one hospital health facility in the city of Purwakarta called AMIRA Hospital. This hospital is an individual private hospital, not under a corporate or group where its competitors have branches in every city and have centralized and integrated service standards. To excel in the Purwakarta area with its competitors, which are generally large hospitals with a total of 11 hospitals including 10 private hospitals and 1 regional hospital. AMIRA hospitals must improve services that are oriented towards patient satisfaction, which is an important factor in staying afloat and superior among its competitors. Among the many types of healthcare facilities, hospitals play an important role in meeting the needs of their patients. Regarding the number of outpatient visits at RSU AMIRA throughout 2018 - 2021, there has been a consistent decline in the queue for the outpatient clinic every year for the last 3 years. This affects the sustainability and operations of AMIRA Hospital. The following is a picture of the AMIRA RSU poly queue.

Fig. 1: Graph of AMIRA RSU Poly Queue
Source: 2021 AMIRA RSU Registration Counter Report

Meanwhile, RSU AMIRA's hope is that there will be an increase in the number of patient visits every year. Patient characteristics that influence the choice to return to AMIRA Hospital, which in turn influences the level of patient satisfaction and loyalty, as well as costs, inadequate hospital facilities, and unsatisfactory quality of service are

possible causes of this decline in the number of visits. Several patients complained and were dissatisfied with the quality of services provided by RSU AMIRA. As a result, the quality of health care provided falls far short of what patients and society anticipated. When patients are unhappy with the care they receive, it can lead to conflict within their families and, ultimately, public complaints expressed over platforms such as the internet.

Hospital services are the patient's experience as a determinant of whether the patient will return to the hospital. If the patient is satisfied with the services provided by the hospital, the patient will return and recommend the hospital to those closest to him directly or indirectly to the virtual world. However, on the other hand, if the patient is disappointed, the patient will tell about his disappointment. The key to creating customer loyalty is customer satisfaction. As of early 2022, RSU AMIRA's Google Review rating is at 4.0. A good score is obtained based on the Google Review satisfaction assessment, a patient satisfaction index that is monitored or can be seen internally in the hospital or the community itself. Google Review's assessment until the beginning of 2022, behind the good average rating value of 4.0, it is known that respondents who give one star rating by patients or visitors to RSU AMIRA is still high. That is, the position of the 1 (one) star chart is in second place after the 5 (five) star chart. It can be concluded that a high number of patients or visitors to AMIRA General Hospital are still dissatisfied with AMIRA General Hospital's services.

According to Limakrisna and Ali (2016), the level of patient satisfaction is defined as the difference between their expectations and actual performance or results. Thus, satisfaction is proportional to dissatisfaction with actual performance relative to one's expectations. Consumers or clients will be dissatisfied if the results fall short of their expectations and very satisfied if they meet or exceed them. Patient satisfaction is an interesting thing to research, because so far the issue of patient satisfaction with hospital services has often been in the public spotlight. RMOLJABAR media report stated that the West Java DPRD continues to be committed to improving the quality of health services at regional hospitals and community health centers. Thus, the existence of health facilities in West Java is increasingly beneficial for the community. Patient satisfaction in research can be influenced by patient trust. Patient trust is all the knowledge possessed by the patient and all the conclusions made by the patient about the objects, attributes and benefits of the medical personnel process (Mowen and Minor, 2012: 213). Due to the inherent dangers and unknowns in health and health care, particularly for vulnerable patients who rely on the skill and good faith of their healthcare providers, the idea of trust is crucial in this field (Alaszewski, 2003). Perceptions of better care, increased acceptance and adherence to prescribed therapy, less worry about care, and other positive outcomes have all been linked to high levels of trust, and reported facilitated access to health services (Jackson et al., 2004). The costs of services offered to

customers must be competitive and in accordance with the benefits of the services offered, so that the prices offered are taken into consideration by customers when making decisions to determine the choice of hospital. Before determining costs, hospitals must be able to pay attention to the factors that influence them so that cost determination can compete with similar hospitals. Cost perception becomes patient trust and satisfaction with the hospital. It can be concluded that cost perceptions can influence patient trust and satisfaction.

This is in accordance with previous research conducted by Kurnianingrum and Hidayat (2020), Indriana et al. (2021), Olivia and Bernardo (2022), Neupane and in particular, "cost perception has a major influence on patient trust and satisfaction" (Devkota, 2017). But previous research, including Rusandy (2016), suggest further investigation The two independent variables used in this study are all that are needed for future research; Investigations using other independent factors outside the research model are still needed. And research by Neupane and Devkota (2017) recommends using different service quality models to identify more patient/customer satisfaction factors, especially those related to the hospital sector. Based on known background, research gaps, research recommendations from previous research and the results of pre-surveys that have been carried out. Therefore, the author wants to conduct research on "The Influence of Service Quality and Cost Perceptions on Trust and Its Implications for Patient Satisfaction at RSU AMIRA Purwakarta".

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Theory of Consumer Behavior*

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2018: 158), buyers' main shopping habits function as a compass for the consumer goods industry. This includes individuals and families who purchase goods for their own purposes. In Muhammad Firmansyah (2018), consumer behavior is defined as "the process in which customers decide to obtain, use, and consume a good or service, including elements that influence product purchases and usage choices" (Lamb, Hair, and Mc Daniel). To fulfill their desires and goals, consumers engage in what is known as consumer behavior, which includes the mental states of individuals or groups throughout the phases of product discovery, evaluation, purchase, and use.

B. *Patient Satisfaction*

When consumers evaluate a product or service based on how well it performs, the result is customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is directly correlated with the extent to which performance meets or exceeds expectations (Kotler and Keller, 2016: 153). Customers use the word "customer satisfaction" to describe a collection of open behaviors connected to a product or service, as stated by Supranto (2016: 44). When consumers evaluate their actual experience purchasing a product or service against their expectations, they will have a sense of customer

satisfaction. In short, people want to be able to buy useful things at a reasonable price. By making the best use of their resources, businesses aim to meet customer expectations and fulfill their desires.

C. Patient Trust

Important aspects that will influence customer choices include consumer sentiment. Attitudes, beliefs, and behavior are all interconnected ideas. Building trust is critical for every organization. A key component in developing client loyalty is building trust in long-term relationships with consumers. This trust must be created from the bottom up and demonstrated, not just acknowledged by other parties or business partners. To encourage long-term connections, in this case customer interactions with brands from certain companies, trust is an important variable, according to Balester et al., (2000), as quoted by Ferrinadewi (2010: 1). Experiences that begin to build trust will be built through these customer connections. On the other hand, trust is defined by Robbins (2013: 193) as the belief that other people will not use their words, actions or policies for their own selfish gain.

D. Service quality

Because quality is relative and depends on various factors, the precise definition may vary from one individual to the next. There are many quality experts who have different opinions about what quality is and how it should be defined. To ensure whether input and output can meet consumer demand or not, Lupiyoadi (2013: 212) defines quality as a set of interrelated traits and qualities. Fulfilling clients' wishes and desires and ensuring accurate delivery to meet customer expectations is the primary goal of service quality. There are three different types of customer expectations (Rust in Tjiptono, 2016: 259). First will expectation, second *should expectation*, third *ideal expectation*. According to Tjiptono (2016: 56), there is a strong correlation between customer satisfaction and service quality. This means that service quality directly affects the satisfaction of service recipients. According to Kotler (2016: 147), customer satisfaction is the extent to which individual sentiments are fulfilled after comparing their expectations with performance or results. A positive and satisfying impression of service quality is formed when the actual experience matches expectations.

E. Price Perception

Price is one element of a flexible marketing mix which can change at any time according to place and time. Prices are not just numbers listed on package labels, they also take many forms and perform many functions. Price is the amount the buyer must pay to obtain the item, according to Kotler and Armstrong (2016: 132). The price of goods or services is the monetary value that buyers are willing to part with in return for the benefits of owning or using them, according to Kotler and Keller (2016: 439). According to Kotler and Armstrong (2016: 52), the price variable contains several elements of main pricing activities which include price lists, discounts, payment periods and discounts.

F. Relationship Between Variables

➤ *The Relationship between Service Quality and Trust*

The level of trust and satisfaction experienced by patients is shaped by the quality of service delivered and the extent to which it aligns with their expectations. The findings are consistent with what Nguyen et al. found (2021), Kurnianingrum & Hidayat (2020), Fatima et al. (2018), Ariffin et al. (2018), Al-Damen (2017) who stated that service quality has a significant positive effect on patient trust and satisfaction. Based on the description above, a hypothesis is put forward:

H1: Patient confidence is significantly and positively impacted by service quality at RSU AMIRA Purwakarta.

➤ *The Relationship between Cost Perceptions and Trust*

Patient confidence and happiness can also be influenced by how they view costs. The term "cost" can refer to the monetary value that customers place on a product or service in exchange for the benefits of owning or utilizing it (Kotler and Keller, 2016: 439). Customers' perceptions of the value of a product or service are influenced by the amount of money they pay for it (Rivai & Zulfitri, 2021). A theory is proposed based on the details given above:

H2: There is a positive and significant influence of price perception on patient trust at RSU AMIRA Purwakarta

➤ *The Relationship between Service Quality and Satisfaction*

When the experience meets expectations, people perceive the service as enjoyable and satisfying. Service quality is considered optimal if it exceeds what patients expect. Conversely, a negative impression of service quality may arise from receiving substandard service. Thus, the ability of service providers to consistently satisfy societal expectations (patients) dictates the quality of services, whether positive or poor. Providing evidence that service quality is a key factor in patients' overall happiness, a study by Nguyen et al. (2021), Kurnianingrum & Hidayat (2020), Fatima et al. (2018), Ariffin et al. (2018), and Al-Damen (2017) have been carried out. A theory is proposed based on the details given above:

H3: There is a positive and significant influence of service quality on patient satisfaction at RSU AMIRA Purwakarta

➤ *The Relationship between Cost Perceptions and Satisfaction*

The costs of services offered to customers must be competitive and in accordance with the benefits of the services offered, so that the prices offered are taken into consideration by customers when making decisions to determine the choice of hospital. Before determining costs, hospitals must be able to pay attention to the factors that influence them so that cost determination can compete with

similar hospitals. It can be concluded that cost perceptions can influence patient trust and satisfaction. This is in accordance with research conducted by Kurnianingrum & Hidayat (2020), Indriana et al. (2021), Olivia & Bernardo (2022) stated that cost perception has a significant effect on patient trust and satisfaction. Based on the description above, a hypothesis is put forward:

H4: Price perception has a substantial and favorable impact on patient satisfaction at RSUD AMIRA Purwakarta.

➤ *Trust Mediates Service Quality on satisfaction*

When customers' wants, needs, and expectations are satisfied via transactions, they are likely to buy from you again. Prior work by Al-Damen (2017) shown a favorable and statistically significant relationship between patient happiness and service quality via the medium of trust. Customer satisfaction can only rise in tandem with an improvement in service quality and a subsequent rise in trust. However, satisfaction will decline if treatment quality is deteriorating and patients lose faith in the healthcare provider. An assumption is made from the given description:

H5: The connection between service quality and patient satisfaction is moderated by the trust established with the patient.

➤ *Trust Mediates Cost to Satisfaction*

When customers are happy with their purchase, it is because they worked hard to earn it. A company's success depends heavily on customer happiness. When customers evaluate a product or service based on their expectations

and actual circumstances, the result is consumer satisfaction. Kurnianingrum and Hidayat (2020) found that costs mediated by customer trust significantly and positively influence satisfaction. Based on the description above, a hypothesis is put forward:

H6: Patient trust mediates the relationship between cost and patient satisfaction

➤ *The Relationship of Trust to Customer Satisfaction*

Perceived improved care, higher rates of treatment acceptance and adherence, less worry about care, and easier access to health services are just a few of the numerous advantages linked to high levels of trust.(Jackson et al., 2004).Patient satisfaction is affected by the degree to which patients have faith in the excellence of the hospital's services. Ratnasari and Damayanti's findings corroborate this (2020), Laura (2017), Rusandy (2016), Sari et al. (2019), Beyari (2020), Chou, Shi-Kai, Kohsuwan; Thanabordeekij (2019) claims that patients' level of confidence in healthcare providers greatly influences their level of satisfaction with those providers.. The trust variable was chosen because patient trust can support the creation of patient satisfaction and this patient trust has been widely studied by previous researchers with varying results. Based on the description above, a hypothesis is put forward:

H7: At RSUD AMIRA Purwakarta, patient satisfaction is positively and significantly impacted by patients' faith in the healthcare provider. The following may be done to construct a conceptual framework based on the framework of thought:

Fig. 2: Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHOD

A quantitative descriptive research strategy based on a causality approach was used in this research. This research is an example of a causality study. Several theoretical frameworks relating to service quality characteristics,

patient trustworthiness perceptions, and consequences for patient satisfaction were consulted during the problem formulation and hypothesis development phases of the study, which were based on a literature review. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to patients at RSUD AMIRA Purwakarta. After that, data

analysis, statistical calculations, and data interpretation are used to describe and analyze all research topics. This research utilizes primary data, namely data collected directly from surveys by sending questionnaires and then compiling the responses. All patients who visited RSU AMIRA Purwakarta as outpatients constituted the study population. The analytical approach used in this work, structural equation modeling, was used to vary the sample size. A sample size of 100-200 is considered sufficient, according to the findings of Hair et al. (2014). This research involved 34 research indicators, which means that a minimum of 170 samples, or 5 times the number of predicted indicators, was required. To ensure that the number of respondents was not reduced below the

minimum determined by biased or inaccurate data, a sample size of over 200 was used (Hair et al, 2014). The authors used a *non-probability sampling strategy* based on a purposive sampling approach for this investigation. Using SmartPLS 3.0. PLS, SEM technique is used to test the research hypothesis.

IV. RESULT

Using the tools provided by SmartPLS v.3, researchers in this study tested their hypotheses using SEM analysis. Construct full measurement and structural models using all SEM components.

Fig. 3: Flow diagram (Path Diagram)
Source: 2023 Analysis Data Results

A. Internal Reliability Test

In order to examine the dependability of indicators on a variable, the Composite Reliability value is computed. As

an additional measure, the reliability test may be enhanced by using the Cronbach alpha value.

Table 1: Internal Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
Patient Trust (Z)	0.936	0.946	Reliable
Patient Satisfaction (Y)	0.937	0.947	Reliable
Service Quality (X1)	0.957	0.963	Reliable
Price Perception (X2)	0.928	0.941	Reliable

Source: 2023 Analysis Data Results

Composite reliability ratings for all research variables are > 0.6, ranging from 0.941 to 0.963, as seen in the table above, and Cronbach's alpha values larger than 0.7, with ranges of 0.928 to 0.957. According to these findings,

every study variable has a high degree of dependability as they all fulfilled the requirements. Additionally, as shown in the table below, each variable also makes use of the average variance extracted (AVE) value.

Table 2: Average variance extracted (AVE) value

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Information
Patient Trust (Z)	0.638	Reliable
Patient Satisfaction (Y)	0.643	Reliable
Service Quality (X1)	0.723	Reliable
Price Perception (X2)	0.666	Reliable

Source: 2023 Analysis Data Results

According to the data in the table, all of the variables have an AVE value more than 0.5, with numbers ranging from 0.638 to 0.723. This means that there is excellent convergent validity for all of the variables.

B. Discriminant Validity Test

An indicator is said to have discriminant validity if, when compared to the correlation of that variable with other variables, the square root of its AVE is the biggest, as

determined by a discriminant validity test conducted using the derived AVE value. Fornell-Larcker One method for determining discriminant validity is the criterion. A discriminant validity test finds out whether an indicator is discriminantly valid based on the computed AVE. Significance of discriminant validity in an indicator is determined by whether the square root of the AVE for a specific variable exceeds its correlation with other variables.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity Test (FornellLarcker Criterion)

	Patient Trust (Z)	Patient Satisfaction (Y)	Service Quality (X1)	Price Perception (X2)
Patient Trust (Z)	0.799			
Patient Satisfaction (Y)	0.668	0.802		
Service Quality (X1)	0.727	0.765	0.850	
Price Perception (X2)	0.515	0.679	0.586	0.816

Source: 2023 Analysis Data Results

According to the data in the table, the values that are bolded have an AVE root value higher than either the correlation between the construct and other constructs or the square of the correlation between each construct. All indications meet the requirements, thus it's safe to say they merit more examination.

C. Inner Model Evaluation

➤ *Coefficient of Determination (R²)*

To showcase how much impact the independent variable has on the dependent variable, the assessment of the Coefficient of Determination (R²) can be employed.

Table 4: Coefficient of Determination (R²)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Patient Trust (Z)	0.540	0.536
Patient Satisfaction (Y)	0.680	0.675

Source: 2023 Analysis Data Results

One dependent variable, Patient Trust (Z), is affected by Service Quality (X1) and Price Perception (X2), as shown in the table above. The other dependent variable, Patient Satisfaction (Y), is affected by Service Quality (X1), Price Perception (X2), and Patient Trust (X1) (Z). Patient Trust (Z) was the dependent variable with an adjusted R-Square value of 0.536. Additionally, with an Adjusted R-Square value of 0.675, Patient Satisfaction (Y) was determined to be the dependent variable.

The square root of q (Predictive Relevance)

By analyzing the dependent variable's Q-squared value, Q-Square predictive relevance evaluates the model's ability to generate observed values and parameter estimates using the blindfolding technique.

Table 5: Q-Square Predictive Relevance

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Patient Trust (Z)	2000,000	889,555	0.555
Patient Satisfaction (Y)	2000,000	883,466	0.558
Service Quality (X1)	2000,000	692,660	0.654
Price Perception (X2)	1600,000	691,281	0.568

Source: 2023 Analysis Data Results

The provided result indicates that the Service Quality variable (X1) has a Q2 value of 0.654, the Price Perception variable (X2) has a Q2 value of 0.568, the Patient Trust variable (Z) has a Q2 value of 0.555, and the Patient Satisfaction variable (Y) has a Q2 value of 0.558. (Y). It may be inferred that this study has substantial observational value due to the fact that the Q2 value acquired exceeds 0. F-Square (Effect Size)

The f-square value stipulates the minimum size required to be deemed significant. The values 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 indicate whether the latent variable predictor has a moderate, substantial, or weak structural effect, respectively (Ghozali, 2015).

Table 6: F-Square Value (Effect Size)

	Patient Trust (Z)	Patient Satisfaction (Y)
Patient Trust (Z)		0.044
Service Quality (X1)	0.598	0.256
Price Perception (X2)	0.027	0.214

Source: 2023 Analysis Data Results

A significant F2 value of 0.589 was achieved, surpassing the threshold of 0.35, indicating the impact of Service Quality on Patient Trust. This affirms the presence of a statistically significant association between service quality and patient trust. The subsequent phase involved assessing the effect of service quality on patient satisfaction. An F2 value of 0.256 was found, which is more than 0.35, indicating a strong effect on patient satisfaction from a statistical standpoint. The statistical analysis revealed that the impact of price perception on patient trust is minimal, with an F2 value of 0.027 falling within the range of 0.02 to 0.15. There was a statistically significant relationship between price perception and patient satisfaction (F2 = 0.214, more than 0.35), suggesting that this factor has a significant role in

determining satisfaction levels. Lastly, we found an F2 value of 0.044 for the impact of patient trust on patient trust, which falls within the range of 0.15 to 0.35. This indicates that, statistically speaking, this effect is medium.

➤ *Test the Goodness of Fit Model*

The Goodness of Fit (GoF) is computed by averaging the geometric mean of the average communality scores (AVE values) with the mean of R 2 (as indicated in the endogenous construct). The GoF calculation is as follows: (GoF= $\sqrt{(\text{AVE} \times R^2)}$). P. 177 (Farooq et al., 2018). A good model fit, as defined by Henseler et al. (2016) in (Farooq et al., 2018, p. 177), indicates that the model is plausible and succinct.

Table 7: Goodness of Fit (GoF) Test

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	R Square Adjusted
Patient Trust (Z)	0.638	0.536
Patient Satisfaction (Y)	0.643	0.675
Service Quality (X1)	0.723	
Price Perception (X2)	0.666	
Average	0.667	0.605

Source: 2023 Analysis Data Results

The GoF value can be obtained using the formula $\text{GoF} = \sqrt{(\text{AVE} \times R^2)}$ → $\text{GoF} = \sqrt{(0.667 \times 0.605)}$, namely 0.636. So it can be said that this research model has a GoF large value or the model has a good fit.

This research's hypothesis may be tested using the findings obtained from the data processing that has been done. In this study, we tested our hypotheses by comparing them to the T-Statistics value; if the former is greater than the latter, we may say that our hypothesis is correct.

➤ *Hypothesis testing*

Table 8: Direct Effect Hypothesis Test

Path	Path Coefficient	T statistics	P Values	Information
Patient Confidence (Z) → Patient Satisfaction (Y)	0.175	2,947	0.004	Significant
Service Quality (X1) → Patient Trust (Z)	0.647	11,196	0,000	Significant
Service Quality (X1) → Patient Satisfaction (Y)	0.446	7,955	0,000	Significant
Price Perception (X2) → Patient Confidence (Z)	0.136	2,133	0.034	Significant
Price Perception (X2) → Patient Satisfaction (Y)	0.327	7,055	0,000	Significant

Source: 2023 Analysis Data Results

➤ *Direct Influence*

- It was determined that the path coefficient was positive at 0.647. The T-Statistics value (11.196) is found to be more than the critical value from the T table (1.972), and the P-value (0.000) is < 0.05 ; hence, H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected.
- At 0.136, the path coefficient value is positive. Additionally, the T-Statistics value (2.133) above the critical value from the T table (1.972), and the P-value (0.034) is below 0.05; hence, H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected.
- It was determined that the path coefficient was positive at 0.446. The T-Statistics value (7.955) is found to be bigger than the T table value (1.972), and the P-value (0.000) is < 0.05 ; hence, H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected.
- At 0.327, the path coefficient value was determined to be positive. The T-Statistics value (7.055) is found to be more than the critical value from the T table (1.972), and the P-value (0.000) is < 0.05 ; hence, H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected.
- At 0.175, the path coefficient value is positive. Additionally, the T-Statistics value (2.947) above the critical value from the T table (1.972), and the P-value (0.000) is below 0.05; hence, H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected.

➤ *Indirect Influence*

- A positive value of 0.113 was determined for the path coefficient. Hypothesis H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted since the T-Statistics value (2.801) is higher than the T table value (1.972) and the P-value (0.006) is < 0.05 .
- A positive value of 0.074 was determined for the path coefficient. Hypothesis H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted since the T-Statistics value (2.263) is higher than the T table value (1.972) and the P-value (0.025), which is < 0.05 .

V. DISCUSSION

Service quality and patient trust at RSU AMIRA Purwakarta were determined to have a positive association with a path coefficient value of 0.647. Along with the fact that the P-value (0.000) is < 0.05 and the T-Statistics value (11.196) is higher than the T table value (1.972), it is also known that H0 is rejected and H1 is approved. What this suggests is that patient trust is significantly and positively impacted by service quality (X1) in a one-way fashion (Z). This clarifies that a higher Service Quality score will lead to a greater level of patient trust. Similarly, a decline in patient trust is likely to occur in the event that the Service Quality score is poor. At RSU AMIRA Purwakarta, researchers discovered a positive correlation of 0.136 between patients' perceptions of prices and their confidence in the institution. We may reject H0 and accept H1 since the T-Statistics value (2.133) is larger than the T table value (1.972) and the P-value (0.034) is less than 0.05. What this indicates is that Price Perception (X2) has a strong positive effect on Patient Trust, and this effect is

unidirectional (Z). Patient Trust will rise in direct proportion to the quality of the Price Perception value. And vice versa: patients will have less faith in the system if they see a poor value in the price. Kurnianingrum and Hidayat's (2020) study backs up these findings by showing that consumers' confidence in a brand is positively correlated with their pricing perception, and that trust in a brand is positively correlated with their desire to return.

At RSU AMIRA Purwakarta, patient satisfaction is positively correlated with service quality ($p = 0.446$). T-Statistics (7.955) also outshines T-table (1.972) and P-value (0.000), both of which are less than 0.05. This leads us to believe that H1 is correct and reject H0. Results show that there is a strong, positive, and unidirectional relationship between Service Quality (X1) and Patient Satisfaction (Y). According to this, the correlation between Service Quality and Patient Satisfaction is positive and grows as the score rises. In a similar vein, Patient Satisfaction will fall or remain low if the Service Quality score goes down. Similarly, Chenhui Jin et al. (2022) found that patients' level of comfort significantly affects their level of satisfaction with the quality of hospital treatments they get. The findings of Novitasari (2022) corroborate this idea, showing that high-quality treatment greatly increases patients' happiness. There was a positive path correlation of 0.327 between patients' perceptions of price and their level of satisfaction at RSU AMIRA Purwakarta. We may reject H0 and accept H1 since the T-Statistics value (7.055) is larger than the T table value (1.972) and the P-value (0.000) is less than 0.05. This indicates that Patient Satisfaction is significantly impacted by Price Perception (X2) in a favorable and unidirectional way (Y). This clarifies that the relationship between Price Perception and Patient Satisfaction. In a similar vein, Patient Satisfaction will fall or remain low if the Price Perception value is poor. Research by Witama and Keni (2020) corroborate the findings of the aforementioned studies by demonstrating a relationship between patients' perceptions of cost and their level of satisfaction with their care.

At RSU AMIRA, we found that trust moderates the relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction. Proving this point is the achievement of a positive route coefficient value of 0.175. We may reject H0 and accept H1 since the T-Statistics value (2.947) is larger than the T table value (1.972) and the P-value (0.000) is less than 0.05. This indicates that Patient Trust (Z) has a positive and unidirectional effect on Patient Satisfaction (Y). The correlation between a high Patient Trust score and high Patient Satisfaction is seen below. Similarly, a decline in patient satisfaction is likely to accompany a worsening of the patient trust score. Consistent with findings from the study by Lestariningsih et al. (2018), which demonstrate that trusting a provider increases patient happiness, which in turn increases loyalty. Similarly, Alrubaiee (2011) said that patients' confidence in healthcare providers is significantly influenced by their level of satisfaction with those providers, and that patients' views of the quality of those services have a positive and powerful effect on both.

Furthermore, the findings revealed that at RSU AMIRA Purwakarta, the connection between cost and satisfaction was influenced by patient trust, as indicated by the positive path coefficient value of 0.113. The rejection of H₀ and acceptance of H₁ is warranted since the T-Statistics value (2.801) exceeds the T table value (1.972), and the P-value (0.006) is less than 0.05. This signifies that Patient Trust (Z) could act as a mediator in the relationship between Service Quality (X₁) and Patient Satisfaction (Y), with Service Quality (X₁) exerting a substantial positive (unidirectional) impact on Patient Satisfaction (Y). This clarifies the intricate interplay among Service Quality, Patient Trust, and Patient Satisfaction, illustrating how improvements in one aspect can lead to enhancements in the others. Financial considerations, service quality (care of medical personnel, procedural procedures, and tangibles), and patient pleasure are all influenced by the hospital's image, according to FirasAlomari (2022), who made a similar point.

Last but not least, researchers at RSU AMIRA Purwakarta discovered that patients' trust affected their level of pleasure. With a value of 0.074, the path coefficient is positive. It is possible to reject H₀ and accept H₁ since the T-Statistics value (2.263) is more than the T table value (1.972) and the P-value (0.025) is < 0.05. What this means is that there is a strong positive (unidirectional) influence of price perception (X₂) on patient satisfaction (Y), and that patient trust (Z) may function as a moderator between these two variables (Y). The correlation between a high Price Perception value and a high level of patient trust is seen here, which will indirectly increase the Patient Satisfaction value. Similar to the research results above were expressed by Rahmatang (2018) who explained that hospital image has no effect on patient satisfaction and that service quality and cost perceptions affect patient satisfaction. Likewise, research results from Bartlett et al., (2019) explained that patients reported very high satisfaction and confidence in treatment.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research results above, it can be concluded that in a direct relationship there is a significant positive (unidirectional) influence on Service Quality (X₁) on Patient Trust (Z). Additionally, a substantial positive (unidirectional) impact was seen between Price Perception (X₂) and Patient Trust (Z). Patient Trust is thereafter significantly and unidirectionally enhanced by Price Perception (X₂) (Z). The relationship between pricing perception (X₂) and patient satisfaction (Y) was similarly found to be significantly favorable and unidirectional. Additionally, a noteworthy positive correlation (unidirectional) was seen in the association between Patient Satisfaction and Patient Trust (Z) (Y). Moreover, within the framework of the indirect relationship, Service Quality (X₁) exerts a substantial positive (unidirectional) impact on Patient Satisfaction (Y) via Patient Trust (Z); furthermore, the Patient Trust variable (Z) serves as a mediator between Service Quality and Patient Satisfaction. The same results

were also shown in the significant positive (unidirectional) influence of Price Perception (X₂) on Patient Satisfaction (Y) through Patient Trust (Z) and also the Patient Trust variable (Z) was able to mediate the influence of Price Perception on Patient Satisfaction.

It is recommended for company management to pay attention to the results of the lowest mean value on research variables such as service quality regarding statements about the appearance of nurses and administrative staff in serving patients, price perceptions regarding statements of very minimal costs in administration costs for each patient, patient beliefs regarding statements that the hospital is capable overcoming existing obstacles, and finally the satisfaction variable regarding statements regarding fast and appropriate examination, treatment and care services.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Alaszewski, H., Alaszewski, A., Potter, J., Penhale, B., & Billings, J. (2003). Life after stroke: reconstructing everyday life. Center for Health Services Studies. *University of Kent*.
- [2]. Al-Damen, R. (2017). Health Care Service Quality and Its Impact on Patient Satisfaction "Case of Al-Bashir Hospital. *International Journal of Business and Management*; Vol. 12, No. 9.
- [3]. Alrubaiee, L., & Alkaa'ida, F. 2011. The mediating effect of patient satisfaction in the patients' perceptions of health care quality - patient trust relationship. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*.
- [4]. Ariffin, Z. Zainal, A.Y. Yaakop, N. Isa. (2018). Service Quality as Drivers of Customer Loyalty and Intention to Switch: Modeling the Mediating Effect of Customer Satisfaction. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7 (3.21) (2018) 43-47.
- [5]. Balester, Elena Delagado dan Munuera-Aleman, J. L. (2000). Brand Trust in the Context of Consumer Loyalty. *European Journal of Marketing*.
- [6]. Bartlett, J.M.S., Ali, A. M., Provenzano, E., Abraham, J., Driver, K., Munro, A.F. (2019). Prognosis of Early Breast Cancer by Immunohistochemistry Defined Intrinsic Sub-types in Patients Treated With Adjuvant Chemotherapy in The NEAT/BR9601 Trial. *International Journal of Cancer*, 133(6).
- [7]. Beyari, H. (2020). The Role of Trust and Its Impacts on Consumer Satisfaction in The Context of Social Commerce. *Journal for Research on Business and Social Science*. Vol. 3 Iss. 9. Chenhui Jin, et al., (2022)
- [8]. Chou, Shi-Kai, Kohsuwan, P. & Thanabordeekij, P. (2019). The Impact of Corporate Image, Service Quality, Trust, and Perceived Value on Chinese Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty: Medical Services in Thailand. *Human Behavior, Development and Society*, Vol. 20 No 3.
- [9]. Farooq, M. S., Salam, M., Fayolle, A., Jaafar, N., & Ayupp, K. (2018). Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in Malaysia airlines: A PLS-

- SEM approach. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 67.
- [10]. Fatima, T., Malik, S. A., & Shabbir, A. (2018). Hospital Healthcare Service Quality, Patient Satisfaction and Loyalty. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 35(6), 1195–1214.
- [11]. Ferrinadewi, Erna. (2010). *Brands and Consumer Psychology, Implications for Marketing Strategy*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu. Firas Alomari (2022)
- [12]. Firmansyah, A. (2018). *Introduction to Management*. 1st Edition. Yogyakarta: Deepublish.
- [13]. Ghozali, I. & Latan, H. (2015). *Partial Least Squares: Concepts, Techniques and Applications using the SmartPLS 3.0 Program*. Semarang: Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
- [14]. Hair, J.F. Jr., Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., & Anderson, R.E. (2014). *Multivariate Data Analysis, Seventh Edition*. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [15]. Henseler. (2016). Testing Measurement in Variances of Composites Using Partial Least Squares. *International Marketing Review*, Vol. 33 No. 3.
- [16]. Indriana, F., Syah, T.Y. Rahmat & Wekadigunawan, C.S.P. (2021). Service Quality, Price, Customer Satisfaction and Word of Mouth in Hospital X Outpatient Services. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Manajemen*.
- [17]. Jackson, M.E., H.Y. Hsiao., D.A. Anderson, R.L. James, and G.F. Mathis. (2004). Effects of purified β -mannanase and commercial product, Hemicell on performance and uniformity in commercial broilers compared with dietary nutrient adjustment. *Poultry Science*. 83(1).
- [18]. Kotler P., dan G. Amstrong. (2016). *Principles of Marketing*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [19]. Kotler, P. & Amstrong. (2018). *Prinsip-prinsip Marketing Edisi Ke Tujuh*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- [20]. Kotler, Philip & Kevin L. Keller. (2016). *Marketing Management. Edisi ke 15*. Penerbit Pearson Education Limited.
- [21]. Kurnianingrum, A. Fitria & Hidayat, A. (2020). The Influence of Service Quality and Price Perception on Consumer Trust and Revisit Intention at Beauty Care Clinic in Indonesia. *Archives of Business Review* – Vol. 8, No.6.
- [22]. Laura, N. (2016). The Effect of Trust and Service Quality Toward Patient Satisfaction With Customer Value as Intervening Variable. *Binus Business Review*, 7(2), 157-162.
- [23]. Lestariningsih, T., Hadiyati, E., & Astuti, R. (2018). Study of service quality and patient satisfaction to trust and loyalty in public hospital, Indonesia. *International Journal of Business Marketing and Management*, 3(2).
- [24]. Limakrisna, Ali, H. (2016). *Research Methods Practical Hints for Solving Business Problems, Preparation of Theses, Theses, Dissertations*. Jakarta: Open University.
- [25]. Lupiyoadi, Rambat. (2014). *Services Marketing Management. Edition 3*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- [26]. Mowen & Minor. (2012). *Consumer behavior. Volume 1*. Edition. Fifth (translation) Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [27]. Neupane, R. & Devkota, M. (2017). Evaluation of the Impacts of Service Quality Dimensions on Patient/Customer Satisfaction: A Study of Private Hospitals in Nepal. *Int. J. Soc. Sc. Manage*. Vol. 4, Issue-3: 165-176.
- [28]. Nguyen, N. Xuan, Tran, K. & Nguyen, T. Anh. (2021). Impact of Service Quality on In-Patients' Satisfaction, Perceived Value, and Customer Loyalty: A Mixed-Methods Study from a Developing Country. *Patient Preference and Adherence*.
- [29]. Olivia, S. & Bernardo, I. (2022). Effect of Trust, Price Fairness, and Service Quality on Patient Satisfaction at the Dental Studio Clinic, West Jakarta. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*. Vol. 5, no. 3, Pages: 27317-27329.
- [30]. Rahmatang. 2018. Analysis of the Relationship between Handling Facilities, Handling Methods and Transit Time with Fish Quality in Purse Seine Fisheries in Barru Regency and Bulukumba Regency. *[Thesis]*. Marine and Fisheries Science. Hasanuddin University.
- [31]. Ratnasari, I. & Damayanti, S. (2020). The Influence of Service Quality and Patient Trust on the Satisfaction of Class 1 Inpatients of BPJS Participants at RSUD Karawang. *Management Business Journal*. Vol. 3 No.2.
- [32]. Rivai, J., & Zulfitri. (2021). The Role of Purchasing Decisions Mediating Product Quality, Price Perception, and Brand Image on Customer Satisfaction of Kopi Janji Jiwa. *Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 3(2).
- [33]. Robbins, S.P., & Judge, T.A. (2013). *Organizational behavior*. Edition 16. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- [34]. Rusandy, D. Santyo. (2016). The Influence of Service Quality and Trust on Inpatient Satisfaction. *Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship*, Vol. 1, No. 3: 191-205.
- [35]. Sari, W. Puja, Farida, N. & Jati, S. Patria. (2019). The Influence of Hospital Trust and Service Quality to Patient Satisfaction and Loyalty. *The 2nd International Conference on Inclusive Business in the Changing World*.
- [36]. Supranto. (2016). *Statistik Teori dan Aplikasi Edisi Kedelapan*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [37]. Tjiptono, Fandy dan G. Chandra. (2016). *Service, Quality & Satisfaction*. Edisi 4. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- [38]. Witama, A., & Keni, K. (2020). The Impact of Brand Image, Perceived Price and Service Quality Toward Customer Satisfaction. *Advances in Social Science Education and Humanities Research*.